

VIRTUAL MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION OF 3D COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Three-dimensional (3D) woven composites have advantages over the more usual composites that are built from many two-dimensional layers and have low through-thickness strength and high cost of production. The 3D woven composites have through-thickness reinforcement and may produce near net-shaped preforms directly from the loom with lower cost. But one of the major reasons that they have not been more widely used by industry is the lack of suitable design tools. The present work addresses this issue through a multi-scale virtual characterisation technique that allows the material properties of complex 3D woven composites to be determined for use in conventional finite element models.

1 INTRODUCTION

The application of advanced materials generally mandates advanced or improved design methodologies. The use of state-of-the-art composite materials as an alternative to traditional engineering materials often fails due to the three-dimensional (3D) nature of many complex structures. One particular reason is the inadequacy of through-thickness performance of the composite material, for which the cause is often the complexity of the manufacturing process to which the material is subjected. 3D weaving is a process that potentially allows automation of the manufacture of complex composite components [1]. It can incorporate fibres through the thickness of the part, a notable benefit over its two-dimensional counterpart. The presence of through-thickness fibres can enhance some mechanical properties of the part, specifically delaying onset of fracture and delamination. The enhancement of such mechanical properties has traditionally been verified only after a representative structure has been woven, fabricated, trimmed and tested. These as-measured or as-tested mechanical properties can then be used in design verification through detailed analysis.

A drawback of the use of 3D woven composites is that the simulation tools available commercially for composite simulation are mainly dedicated to laminated two-dimensional composites and not for 3D woven composites. Better design methods are needed to both evaluate the manufacturing process and also predict the mechanical performance during operations because engineers can no longer assume that some structural part behaves operationally as it was designed. The part's performance is critically affected by how it was produced and the arrangement of fibres within body of the part.

A Virtual Material Characterisation (VMC) process to predict the mechanical properties of 3D woven components is presented herein. This computational approach is proposed as an alternative to one which builds a physical component and then tests it. A benefit of this approach is that the

computational prediction of mechanical properties can be made early in the design of a new component. This provides unparalleled flexibility to explore different design options provided by the 3D weaving process.

Much of the work presented in this paper was done as part of the Breakthrough Aerospace Materials (BAM) project, which is a collaborative research project based in the UK [2] with the aim of developing a procedure to enable the design and manufacture of complex shaped components using 3D woven composites. BAM is led by Sigmatech and joins aerospace companies BAE Systems and Rolls-Royce along with ESI Group, MSC Software, Antich & Sons, M. Wright & Sons, Teledyne CML Composites and three leading universities with expertise in 3D woven composites (Nottingham, Manchester and Bristol). Some of the development of the VMC process, carried out as part of the BAM project, has been reported previously [3]. Pacific ESI's involvement is a small part of the robust industrialisation of the process prior to its exploitation by end-users of ESI Group's VPS product in Europe and elsewhere including those within Australia's aerospace and defence sector.

The VMC process is described in Section 2 with example computations in Section 3 and conclusions are presented in Section 4. The primary computational tool used in this work was Virtual Performance Solution (VPS), a commercial finite element software package from ESI Group [4].

2 VIRTUAL MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION

Modelling of the weaving process is not part of the present work, although the VMC process takes (as input) the fabric architecture created using the kinematic modelling approach developed by the University of Bristol [5] and transferred through the open-source software TexGen developed by the University of Nottingham [6]. The modelling procedure for a 3D textile is outlined in Figure 1. First, a basic loose representation of a unit cell is formed using based on the weave design information (weave architecture, number of fibres per yarn and fibre diameter). Each yarn contains a specified number of chains of 1D beam elements to which negative strains are applied drawing the fabric together. Contact models allow the interactions both inside and outside the yarns to be captured. Therefore, the weaving process can be simulated to produce a unit structure (the compacted, multi-filament model) that includes manufacturing effects such as the compression and nestling of fibre bundles that occur in the process. Finally, the compacted geometry is extracted as a TexGen file which may then be used for further analysis.

Figure 1: Modelling procedure for a layer-to-layer 3D woven textile a) initial loose multi-filament model, b) compacted multi-filament model, c) final compacted TexGen Model.

The VMC process provides information which addresses the complexity of 3D textile architecture produced by manufacturing operations. From this information is produced material data suitable for use in standard, homogenised finite element (FE) models. A multi-scale approach was developed to achieve this aim. At the smallest scale (the micro-scale), the stiffness and failure characteristics of unidirectional yarns were computed for a range of fibre volume content (FVC) values. This represents

the material within a yarn of the composite – not the pure matrix material that fills the volumes between the yarns. At the next scale (the meso-scale), a model of the 3D woven composite was created based on the TexGen data for a representative “unit cell” of material (Representative Volume Element or RVE). A mesh based on the TexGen model has fibre orientation and FVC values that vary throughout the volume and these were used to analytically assign the inelastic stiffness and strength properties obtained on the micro scale to the meso-scale 3D solid FE model. The effective stiffness was then determined for the meso-scale RVE through the evaluation of six deformation modes representing the six macroscopic unit strain states. In addition, virtual tensile tests in all three major directions (warp, weft and out-of-plane) have been performed to identify the effective strength properties. The material properties obtained from the meso-scale results were then able to be used in standard FE models with layered anisotropic materials (the macro-scale).

Figure 2 shows a micro-scale RVE of a unidirectional yarn with randomly distributed fibres in a matrix and FVC of 0.4. The model has 480,000 hexahedral solid elements. A series of such models were created which spanned the full range of local FVC that occurred in the 3D woven composite. A phenomenological orthotropic damage model was used for the fibres and an isotropic elasto-plastic model with damage for the pure matrix phase. Nodal displacements were constrained so as to impose periodic boundary conditions on the RVE [7]. Each micro-scale model was subjected to deformations consistent with a series of average strain states. Curves describing the average or effective stress as a function of effective strain of the micro-scale models (Figure 3) were used to characterise the yarn failure properties as a function of FVC for use in the meso-scale models.

Figure 2: Micro-scale RVE of a unidirectional composite (FVC = 0.4).

Figure 4 shows a meso-scale RVE for a 3D woven composite. The colours indicate parts of the model with different material properties. The model has 881,200 hexahedral solid elements. Each finite element in the meso model has stiffness and strength properties based on the local FVC as determined from the micro-scale models. Nodal displacements of the meso-scale RVE were constrained in a similar manner to micro-scale RVE models such that periodic boundary conditions were imposed. For this example, the RVE was notionally divided into 13 layers through the thickness so that section forces could be extracted on the four sides of each layer plus the total in each of the x, y and z directions. The RVE was subjected to a set of deformations consistent with a series of six average strain states $(\epsilon_{xx}, \epsilon_{yy}, \epsilon_{zz}, \gamma_{xy}, \gamma_{yz}, \gamma_{zx})$. Linear analyses were used to obtain homogenised elastic properties for the individual layers through the thickness, while non-linear analyses were used to estimate the corresponding failure parameters for each layer. This is referred to as the reduced meso model. The elastic and failure properties thus obtained were then available for macro-scale analyses of the given 3D woven composite but with far fewer elements per volume than were required for the meso-scale model. Similar material properties determined for a single homogeneous layer over the full thickness of the composite were also obtained (referred to as the homogeneous model).

Figure 3: Effective stress strain curves of unidirectional micro-scale RVE for different loading conditions and FVC.

Figure 4: Meso-scale RVE of a 3D woven composite.

3 EXAMPLE RESULTS

The results of the Virtual Material Characterisation process for a vacuum infused layer-to-layer carbon fibre 3D composite were used in macro-models of two tests (four-point bending test and corner bend test) in order to provide a validation of the method. In both cases the specimen thickness was 4.3 mm which is the same as the meso-scale RVE used for the determination of the material properties.

3.1 Four-Point Bending Test

The arrangement of the four-point bending test model is presented in Figure 5. There were 13

layers of solid elements through the thickness and a total of 77,460 hexahedral elements. The supports and load application bars were rigid bodies. Results of simulations and experiment are compared in Figure 6 for total vertical force against vertical displacement of the load application bars. Two simulations were run – one with the material properties varying through the specimen thickness (the reduced meso model) and the other with uniform properties through the thickness (the homogeneous model). The homogeneous model was too stiff by about 20% while the reduced meso model slightly underestimated the stiffness. For both simulations the displacement at peak load was approximately 10% less than for the experiment. Overall, the reduced meso model displayed superior performance to that of the homogeneous model.

Figure 5: Four-point bending test model.

Figure 6: Comparison of experiment and simulation for the four-point bending test.

3.2 Corner Bend Test

The corner bend test gives some insight into the through-thickness performance of the composite specimen. The arrangement of the model of the corner bend test is shown in Figure 7. There were 13 layers of solid elements through the thickness and a total of 96,850 hexahedral elements. The four cylindrical loading bars were modelled as rigid bodies. A comparison of force-displacement for simulation and experiment is presented in Figure 8, where the total vertical force is plotted against the

relative vertical displacement of the upper and lower load bars. The simulation with the homogeneous material model consistently overestimated the stiffness and strength of the specimen. The simulation with the reduced meso model was also somewhat too stiff, except in the early stages of loading, but the peak load was well-predicted albeit at a smaller displacement than in the experiment. As well, the post-peak degradation was not accurately modelled. The performance of the reduced meso model is encouraging but the results of the corner bend test indicate that further refinement may be necessary.

Figure 7: Corner bend test model.

Figure 8: Comparison of experiment and simulation for the corner bend test.

4 CONCLUSIONS

While 3D woven composites offer a way to overcome the drawbacks of low through-thickness strength and high cost of conventional composites for complex structural shapes, there has been a slow adoption of the technology due to the lack of simulation tools for determining their properties. The ability to determine material properties is invaluable to designers at the concept phase of the design process. The Virtual Material Characterisation process discussed herein shows how stiffness and failure properties for complex 3D woven structures may be predicted prior to manufacture. A multi-scale approach was developed (micro-scale, meso-scale and macro-scale). At the micro-scale the

stiffness and strength were determined for a range of unidirectional plies with different fibre volume contents representing the material within yarns of the 3D textile composite. At the meso-scale, a Representative Volume Element of the 3D textile composite was subdivided into a large number of elements with different fibre volume contents and fibre orientations. Properties were assigned based on the properties obtained for the micro-scale models. The stiffness and strength of the meso-scale RVE was determined for the full thickness of the composite divided into a number of layers. The anisotropic material properties thus determined for the 3D textile composite were then available for use in the macro-scale model.

Two validation examples have been provided with simulations of a four-point bending test and a corner bend test with a vacuum infused layer-to-layer carbon fibre 3D textile composite. Two material modelling schemes were used: the homogeneous model in which the same properties were used throughout the thickness, and the reduced meso model in which the properties varied through the thickness in layers. The homogeneous model consistently overpredicted the stiffness and strength of the specimens in both tests. The reduced meso model was reasonably accurate for the four-point bending test, but its performance for the corner bend test indicates that further refinement may be necessary to improve through-thickness behaviour.

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